
Monetary Policy and Agricultural Sector Gross Domestic Product Performance in Nigeria

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Abstract: This study investigates the links between monetary policy and agricultural sector gross domestic product performance in Nigeria from 1980-2023 using the unit root test, co-integration test and error correction method. The study revealed the presence of a positive relationship between monetary policy and agricultural sector performance and showed that the variables are co-integrated within the period under consideration. The study from the ECM result shows that the short run equilibrium is able to link to the long run equilibrium to the speed of -0.684141 or 68 under the period of consideration, 1980-2023 in the economy of Nigeria. The study concludes that government should make policy that will give farmers access to credit to enhance productivity and growth in the sector thus providing enabling environment to produce imported goods here in Nigeria to cushion the impact of food scarcity in the Nigerian economy.

Key words: Agriculture, Open Market Operation, Monetary Policy Rate, Cash Reserve Ratio, Minimum Rediscount Rate.

Introduction

One macroeconomic management tool that is used to stimulate the economy towards the desired direction is monetary policy viz –a viz the agriculture sector. Agriculture has been defined the science, art, or practice of cultivating the soil, producing crops, and raising livestock and in varying degrees the preparation and marketing of the resulting products (Hezekiah and Enaberue, 2024). Olajide, Akinlami and Tijani (2020) described agricultural sector as the most essential sector of the Nigeria economy which holds a lot of possibilities for the future economic development and growth of the nation as it had done in the past. The agricultural sector serves all other sectors in the economy specifically the industrial sector and at the same time is capable of generating broad-based sustained growth necessary for development (Abuka, Alinda, Minoiu, Peydro and Presbitero, 2019; Onyiriuba, Okoro and Ibe, 2020; Osakwe, Elias and Okonkwo, 2019). This is mostly why the sector is referred to as the bedrock of economic development and growth, especially in the provision of adequate and nutritious food vital for human development. The agricultural sector provides food for domestic consumption and export to needy countries thereby generating foreign exchange which in turn increases the national income in the long run (Ajudua, Ojima and Okonkwo, 2015; Ogolo and Tamunotonye, 2018; Okaforcha, Anumudu, Uwazie and Sule, 2024).

Other contributions of the sector to an economy include; the generation of employment, raw materials for industrial processing, and the rural areas also provide markets for primary inputs and consumer products. In addition, skills developed within the agricultural sector are transferred to other sectors during labour migration whether due to increased productivity or not (Ezihe, Agbugba and Idang, 2017). Additionally, over 65 percent of Nigeria's population depends on agriculture, which contributes roughly 25 percent of GDP and 60 percent of non-oil exports. The agricultural sector is seen as a major way out of poverty and for the achievement of long-term economic development in developing nations (Ekine and Nwaokedibe, 2018; Mashinini, Sotja and Dlamini, 2019; Oboh, Tule, and Ebuh, G.U. (2019; Ogbanje and Okpe, 2022). The sector contributes a significant part of the nation's GDP. Between July and September, 2021, the sector contributed almost 30% of the total GDP (Chigbu and Okonkwo 2014). Governments all over the world drive desired changes in particular sectors of their economy through policy. The policies help to direct resources in favour of a particular goal of government. The problems facing the Nigerian agricultural sector include inadequate capital and credit for start-ups, investment, and expansion of agribusiness (Abiola, Rotdelmwa, Adedoyin, Inegbedion and Olabisi, 2021; Oboh, Tule and Ebuh, 2019). The anticipation is that the government can use the instruments of monetary policy to better the sector.

Monetary policy through its stimulus on the financial sector of the economy plays a foremost role in making credit available to the agricultural sector (Iwegbu and Nwaogwugwu, 2022). Monetary policy refers to the deliberate efforts of the government to use changes in money supply; cost, size, and direction of credit to influence the level of economic activities to achieve desired macroeconomic stability in an economy (Ekpung, Udede, and Uwalaka (2017). Monetary policy influences the economy and the agricultural sector through a variety of channels — interest rates, credit and/or bank lending, asset prices via exchange rates, equity and housing prices which are determined by monetary policy rate, treasury bill rates (Adama, Asaleye, Oye and Ogunjobi, 2018; Eniekezimene, Wodu and Anda-Owei, 2023). In recent times, increasing attention has focused on the sectorial effects of monetary policy given that sectors respond differently to monetary policy shocks. The monetary policy of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) through its influence on the financial sector of the economy is capable of playing a major role in and engineering credit availability to the agricultural sector (Olatunji, 2022; Ekine and Nwaokedibe, 2018; Chigbu and Okonkwo (2014). Despite these measures taken by the monetary authorities in terms of the monetary policies in the economy, the agricultural sector output is still moderately low. Therefore this study anticipates to examine how monetary policy instruments can be used to transform the agricultural sector of the Nigerian economy.

Statement of the Problem

Prior to the discovery of crude oil in commercial quantity in Nigeria, the country was a foremost exporting agricultural produce, principally commodities like palm oil, groundnuts, cotton, cocoa, palm kernel, and rubber. Eventually with the passage of time and the rising need for oil prices in the international markets, concentration in the agricultural sector began to deteriorate or debauched extremely. Worse still, Nigeria appears to no longer be able to produce sufficient food for the country's humongous and rapidly growing population. The average annual rate of real output growth from the agricultural sector stood at 5.6% in 2010 to 1.5% in 2012 and 1.3% in 2014. Nevertheless, there was a minuscule or little rise up to 4.42% and in 2016 and 2020 respectively. A key challenge facing Nigeria agricultural sector is the ineffectiveness to capture the financial service requirements of farmers and agribusiness owners who constitute about 65 percent of the population of Nigeria and predominantly rural areas. The agricultural sectors requires access to loans to purchase land and equipment and to invest in the development of new products, services, production technologies and marketing strategies. However, banks are often unwilling to lend money to farmers for agricultural enterprises owing to the dearth of creditability and collateral. Many studies have revealed that monetary policy outcome causes shocks to the economy in general while others discovered a long-run impacts on the agricultural sector. In Nigeria, most studies overlooked the impact of key monetary policy instruments such as monetary

policy rate, open market operation, treasury bill rate. Against this background, this study contributes to the existing literature by investigating the impacts of monetary policy on Nigeria's agricultural output in both the short run and long run on the agricultural sector in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to study monetary policy variables and agricultural sector performance in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the effect of cash reserve ratio and agricultural output in Nigeria,
- ii. Study the impact of liquidity ratio and agricultural output in Nigeria,
- iii. Evaluate the outcome of monetary policy rate and agricultural output in Nigeria,
- iv. Estimate the result of minimum reserve ratio and agricultural output in Nigeria,
- v. Study the impact of open market operation and agricultural output in Nigeria;
- vi. Investigate the outcome of treasury bill and agricultural output in Nigeria.

Study Hypothesis

H₁: increased cash reserve ratio, increases agricultural output in Nigeria,

H₂: increased liquidity ratio, increases agricultural output in Nigeria,

H₃: increased monetary policy rate, increases agricultural output in Nigeria,

H₄: increased minimum reserve ratio, increases agricultural output in Nigeria,

H₅: increased open market operation, increases agricultural output in Nigeria,

H₆: increased treasury bill, increases agricultural output in Nigeria.

Theoretical Literature Reviewed

This serves to as the analytical framework of the study which provides a foundation for our empirical analysis. Theories that relate to the study questions and hypothesis in terms of the impact of monetary policy on agricultural output are examined.

Keynes Liquidity Preference Theory of Money

The theory in Keynes (1936) explains how the supply and demand for money determine interest rates. Keynes called the aggregate demand for money in the economy "liquidity preference". He also stressed the connection between interest rates and the supply and demand for money. The approach to the demand for money is based on two important functions. Firstly, the medium of exchange and secondly store of value. Keynes explained the theory of demand for money with the following questions. i). Why do people prefer liquidity? ii). What are the determinants of liquidity preference? People require money to carry out day-to-day transactions but most of them receive income once a month. Individuals hold cash in order to bridge the interval between the receipt of income and its expenditure. This is regarded as transactionary demand for money. Precautionary motive for holding money refers to the desire of the people to hold cash balances for unforeseen contingencies. The cash held under speculative demand for money is used to make speculative gains by dealing in bonds whose prices fluctuate. Keynes holds that the transaction and precautionary motives are relatively interest inelastic, but are highly income elastic. The Keynesians believe that the money supply, through its transmission mechanism, has an indirect effect on the real gross domestic product. Monetarists while agreeing with Keynes that in the short run, the economy does not operate at full employment, therefore expansionary monetary policy may work positively in the long-run, support classists that rising money supply will increase inflation only.

Therefore, they suggest that the policy must accommodate the increase in real GDP without changing the price level. Most of the modern economists are of the view that long-run growth

depends upon the enhancement of productivity. If an appropriate monetary policy is supplemented by the external environment of suitable liquidity, interest rate, robust demand, soft assistance from the World Bank or the financial institutions and debt rescheduling would lead to sustainable economic growth in the long run. Monetarists strongly believe that monetary policy exerts a greater impact on economic activity as an unanticipated change in the stock of money affects output and growth, i.e. the stock of money must increase unexpectedly for the central bank to promote economic growth. They are of the opinion that an increase in government spending would crowd out the private sector and such can outweigh any short-term benefits of an expansionary fiscal policy. On the other hand, the concept of the liquidity trap, which is a situation in which real interest rates cannot be reduced by any action of the monetary authorities, was introduced by Keynesian economics.

Empirical Literature Reviewed

Hezekiah and Enaberue (2023) investigates monetary decisions as it affect Nigeria agricultural sector from 1981- 2016. The four agricultural sub-sectors that were examined were crop production, forestry, fishery, and livestock. Other variables that were employed in this research were the over lending rate, benchmark interest rate, money stock, and forex rate. In addition, general level of prices and other economic activity in the economy as a whole were taken into account. The results show that the agricultural sector as a whole and its several subsectors have no effect on unexpected tightening of benchmark interest rate over the period; nonetheless, the agricultural sector is directly affected by shocks to monetary policy through the channels of interest rates and liquidity preference. The term reveal that long-term effects of the forex rate and broad money supply are significant. Throughout money supply channel's ability to disperse imbalance in the agricultural owing bench mark interest rate remained limited. The study revealed that strengthening policy rate, access to loan and lending rate will support Nigeria's agriculture sector's growth. Momoh, Isere and Al-hassan (2023) investigated monetary policy give its impact on the financial sector of the economy and the roles it plays in making credit available to the agricultural sector. This study I lie with above statement, empirically examined the impact of monetary policy on agricultural output in Nigeria for a period of 40years (1981 – 2021). The study relied on secondary data for our analysis which were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and National Bureau of statistics (NBS).

Methodology

The methodology for this study employs a time-series econometric approach to analyze the impact of monetary policy on agricultural sector performance in Nigeria from 1980 to 2023. Data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), focusing on key monetary policy instruments such as the monetary policy rate, cash reserve ratio, liquidity ratio, minimum rediscount rate, open market operations, and treasury bill rates. The study applied unit root tests to examine stationarity properties of the variables, followed by the Johansen co-integration test to establish long-run relationships among the variables. To analyze the short- and long-term effects of monetary policy on agricultural GDP, the error correction model (ECM) was employed. The ECM results revealed that monetary policy instruments significantly influence agricultural GDP, with a short-run equilibrium adjusting towards the long-run equilibrium at a speed of $-0.68.4141$. The study confirms that liquidity provisions through monetary policy channels, including treasury bills and open market operations, play a crucial role in agricultural sector growth. The econometric findings emphasize the need for policymakers to enhance financial access for farmers by adjusting liquidity ratios and interest rates to stimulate agricultural productivity. The study further suggests that government intervention in credit provision can strengthen agricultural sector performance by mitigating financial constraints. This approach provides a robust framework for understanding the dynamic link between monetary policy and agricultural output, reinforcing the necessity for a balanced monetary policy that supports sustainable agricultural development.

Results and Discussion

The study used ratio of Agricultural output to GDP (AGR GDP) as the dependent variable and Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Treasury Bill Rate (TBR), Money supply (MS), Lending Rate (LENR) and Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) as independent variables. The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) stationarity test, Johanson cointegration technique and adopted the Auto regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) procedure introduced by Persaran Smith and Shin for the estimation were adopted. The results revealed that there is a long run relationship between dependent and the independent variables. The result further shows that the main monetary policy instruments (MPR, LENR, MS, and TBR) and money supply were significant while ACGSF was not statistically significant. It was found out that money supply, lending rate, treasury bill rates and monetary policy rate are important drivers of agricultural output. The study therefore recommends among others: The Central Bank of Nigeria should supervise the disbursement of the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund and ensure that the funds are properly channeled to the agricultural sector; Lending rate should be reduced to encourage borrowing and hence expand investment and productivity in the agricultural sector. Tajudeen, Salihu, and Yahya (2023) study examines the relationship between monetary policy and commercial banks credit to agricultural sector in Nigeria with uses of secondary data for the period 1981 to 2021 by applying Autoregressive Distributed Lag technique. Result from this study shown that, liquidity ratio, monetary policy rate, loan to deposit ratio and cash reserve ratio have no significant influence on commercial banks credit to agricultural sector in Nigeria.

On the other hand, the treasury bill ratios has significant positive effect on commercial banks credit allocated to agricultural sector in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that Central Bank of Nigeria should cuts down the cash reserve ratio to encourage the loanable funds available with the banks. Regulatory authority should put in place suitable policy that will prevailing cash hoarding in the economy to achieve desired liquidity ratio level. CBN should use the loan to deposit to center for regulating and moderating commercial banks for a positive significant impact to sectors in Nigeria. Authorities should use monetary policy rate to expand the volume of commercial banks' ability to grant credits. Finally, monetary policy authority should ensure that holding of treasury bills by commercial banks should be reduced to enhance the ability to grant loans and advances to the public for productive purposes. Orji (2022) examined monetary policy channels, agriculture sectorial outputs and sustainable growth in the ECOWAS region: a rigorous analysis and implications for policy. Data from the World Bank and International Monetary Fund over 2013–2019 were sourced for thirteen member countries. The study adopted the Driscoll–Kraay fixed-effects ordinary least squares regression (OLS) estimator. The findings revealed that while the effect of monetary policy channels on the agricultural sector value added is largely heterogeneous and significantly in-elastic, the ones on the industrial and services sectors are overwhelmingly homogeneous and negative, but insignificant for the services sector.

Moreover, the effect of monetary policy channels on sustainable economic growth is also homogeneously asymmetric, with imminent stagflation while the interactive effects of monetary policy channels are heterogeneous on sustainable economic growth and economic sectors. Therefore, an inflation-targeting monetary policy stance is generally recommended with prioritized exchange rate stabilization amid sufficient fiscal space. Iwegbu and Nwaogwugwu (2022) study examines the relative impact of monetary policy stance and the activities of development finance institutions on agricultural sector performance. The study asserts that the relatively unchanged monetary policy stance of the Central Bank weakens its effectiveness on agricultural sector performance as empirically proven and thus, this study employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) with data spanning through 1981 till 2019 to achieve its objective. The results from the study show that although the monetary policy is effective in stimulating the activities of the agricultural sector in the short run, it is not in ensuring long term improvements of the sector in the long run. However, the activities of the development finance institutions proved effective in enhancing the productivity of the sector by providing liquidities on a long-term basis. The policy implication of this study is that the conventional

monetary policy does not stimulate long term improvements in the agricultural sector while activities of the development finance institutions such as the provision of loans are more effective in stimulating the performance of the sector. Monetary authority through regulations will need to devise more effective ways of empowering the ability of the development finance institutions to mobilize financial resources that are needed for the stimulation of the activities of the sector.

Asaleye, Rotdelmwa, Lawal, Inegbedion and Popoola (2021) study examines the impact of monetary policy channels on agricultural performance in Nigeria using structural vector autoregression (SVAR) and dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS). The study uses output employment and export as metrics for agricultural performance, and the channels of monetary policy considered are credit, interest rate, money and exchange rate. The SVAR variance decomposition findings show that the forecast error shocks of monetary policy channels affect agricultural performance. Likewise, the long-run equations from the DOLS show that output has a positive relationship with money supply, a negative relationship between employment and interest rate, and a negative relationship between exchange rate and export. Based on the findings, the study suggests that the Nigerian government should look beyond the primary objective of stabilizing the economy via money supply and interest rate and consider the secondary benefits of bolstering output and employment in the agricultural sector.

Arigor, Asuquo, Ibeagwa (2021) study analyzed the effects of monetary policy on Agricultural Gross Domestic Product performance in Nigeria, 1970-2018. The specific objectives of the study were to determine the effect of; Exchange rate (EXR), monetary policy rate (MPR), Broad money supply (M2), Liquidity ratio (LIQ), Lending rate (LRT), Reserves deposit money bank (RCBN), Credit by commercial banks to Agric. sector (CREDIT), Inflation (INF) on the Agricultural Gross Domestic Product (AGDP) in Nigeria. Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Philip Peron unit root tests was conducted on the specified time series. It was observed that only two variables; inflation (INF) and liquidity ratio (LIQ) were stationary at levels while others; (CREDIT, DCBN, INT, M2 and MPR) became stationary at first difference. The co-integration and error correction models (ECM) technique was employed in the analysis. The results revealed that in the long run; exchange rate and credit to the agricultural sector were positively signed and significant at the 1 & 5 % levels respectively, while inflation rate was significant at 10 %. In the short run, there exist a negative relationship with respect to lending rate, monetary policy rate and credit to the agricultural sector and are significant at 1%, 10%, and 10% respectively while inflation was positively related to Agric. GDP and is significant at 5%. The findings call for appropriate short- and long-term economic policy packages that should stimulate investment opportunities in the agricultural sector to increase agricultural GDP performance. Appropriate policy package to stabilize inflation rate in the country should be implemented.

Model Specifications

Arigor, Asuquo and Ibeagwa (2021) study examined the effects of monetary policy on agricultural gross domestic product performance in Nigeria, 1970-2018. The specific objectives of the study were to determine the effect of exchange rate (EXR), monetary policy rate (MPR), broad money supply (M2), liquidity ratio (LIQ), lending rate (LRT), reserves deposit money bank (RCBN), credit by commercial banks to Agric. sector (CREDIT) and inflation rate (INF) on the agricultural gross domestic product (AGDP) in Nigeria

Where:

AGDP = Agricultural gross domestic product

BMS = Broad money supply

CREDIT = Credit by commercial banks to Agric. sector

EXR = Exchange rate

INF = Inflation rate

LIQ = Liquidity ratio

LRT = Lending rate

MPR = Monetary policy rate

RCBN = Reserves deposit money bank

The econometric model becomes

$$AGDP = f(\Omega_0 + \Omega_1 BMS_t + \Omega_2 CREDIT_t + \Omega_3 EXR_t + \Omega_4 IFR_t + \Omega_5 LIQ_t + \Omega_6 LRT_t + \Omega_7 MPR_t + \Omega_8 RCBN_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

This model was chosen because of the similarity of the data. So, the model in this study was modified and presented in a functional form as shown below with the removal of some of the adopted variables. Therefore,

$$AGDP = f(CRR + LQR + OMO + MPR + MRR + TRB + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where:

AGDP = agricultural sector output

CRR = cash reserve ratio

LQR = liquidity ratio

OMO = open market operation

MPR = monetary policy rate

MRR = minimum rediscount ratio

TRB = treasury bill

The functional econometric form of the model is stated as:

$$AGDP_t = \Omega_0 + \Omega_1 CRR_t + \Omega_2 LQR_t + \Omega_3 OMO_t + \Omega_4 MPR_t + \Omega_5 MRR_t + \Omega_6 TRB_t + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where:

AGDP = agricultural sector gross domestic product at 't'

CRR = cash reserve ratio at 't'

LQR = liquidity ratio at t'

OMO = open market operation at 't'

MPR = monetary policy rate at 't'

MRR = minimum rediscount ratio at 't'

TRB = treasury bill at 't'

μ = Error term

Ω_1 = Regression intercept

$\Omega_1 - \Omega_6$ = Coefficients of independent variables.

Unit Root Test

Table 1. ADF Test

Augmented -Dickey Fuller Test							
Variables	Levels			First difference			Order of integration
	ADF Stat	Test critical value (5%)	Remark	ADF Stat	Test critical value (5%)	Remark	
AQS	-0.148786	-2.931404		-7.686831	-3.520787	S	1(1)
CRR	-2.193835	-3.518090		-6.288624	-3.520787	S	1(1)
LQR	-42804168	-3.544284		-6.595122	-3.523623	S	1(1)
OMO	-3.179554	-3.518090		-5.320244	-3.533083	S	1(1)
MPR	-3.629301	-3.518090		-7.657332	-3.520787	S	1(1)
MRR	-2.633422	-3.518090		-8.798701	-3.520787	S	1(1)
TR	-0.057339	-3.622033		-4.430640	-3.622033	S	1(1)

Note: the ADF tests for H_0X_t as $1(1)$ against H_1X_t as $1(0)$

Source: Authors' computation (E.view 13.0)

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is attributed to Dickey and Fuller (1979, 1981). The advantage of ADF is that it modifies for higher order serial correlation by adding lagged difference term on the right-hand side. Entirely the variables were not stationary at levels but they became stationary at their first differences. Entirely, the variables in the model are homogeneous of order one $1(1)$ and in so doing fostering the problem of spurious regression linked with time series data. In order words, the variables could be co-integrated.

Table 2. Johansen Co-integration: (Trace Statistic)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.** Critical Value
None *	0.878646	157.4292	125.6154	0.0001
At most 1	0.601123	87.83084	95.75366	0.1548
At most 2	0.479105	57.50044	69.81889	0.3201
At most 3	0.363482	35.97759	47.85613	0.3975
At most 4	0.281783	21.07007	29.79707	0.3533
At most 5	0.182409	10.14762	15.49471	0.2696
At most 6	0.100675	3.501648	3.841465	0.0613

Source: Authors' computation (E.view 13.0)

From Table 2, the Trace statistics indicates the existence of 1 co-integrating association among the variables at 5 per cent level of significance. The presence of co-integration among the variables displays that there is a clear long-run equilibrium link among the variables under examination. The rule states that, for variables to have long-run equilibrium affiliation there must be at least one co-integrating equation. The Trace statistics therefore revealed the existence of a long-run equilibrium connection among the variables. These results confirms the works of Owolabi and Adegbite (2014), Umeh, Ugwo and Ochuba (2021), Ughulu and Agbonkhese (2020) and Wagan, Chen, Seelro and Shah (2018).

Table 3. Johansen Co-integration: (Max-Eigen Statistic)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.** Critical Value
None *	0.878646	69.59838	46.23142	0.0000
At most 1	0.601123	30.33040	40.07757	0.4025
At most 2	0.479105	21.52284	33.87687	0.6445
At most 3	0.363482	14.90752	27.58434	0.7555
At most 4	0.281783	10.92245	21.13162	0.6551
At most 5	0.182409	6.645968	14.26460	0.5318
At most 6	0.100675	3.501648	3.841465	0.0613

Source: Authors' computation (E.view 13.0)

Similarly, from Table 3, the Maximum-Eigen statistic indicates one co-integrating equation at 5 per cent level of significance as a result signifying the rejection of the null hypothesis of zero co-integrating link. This is established by the fact that the Max-Eigen statistic value is greater than the critical value at 5 per cent level of significance. Accordingly, there is a long-run equilibrium affiliation between the dependent variables and the independent variables within the period under review. Impetuously, both the Trace and Max-Eigen test statistic confirms the existence of a long-run equilibrium link between the variables and the hypothesized prerequisites for the period under consideration i.e. 1980 - 2023. We subsequently reject the null hypotheses of no co-integration amongst the variables but we do not reject the alternative hypotheses. On the bases of the result from the Johansen co-integration test which established the existence of a long run link among the variables, we therefore have the confidence to conduct the short run dynamic adjustment. Thus, we proceed to estimate an over-parameterized error correction model from where the parsimonious error correction mechanism was obtained. Agbonkhese and Asekome (2016), Mashinini, Sotja, Dlamini and Dlamini (2019) and Momoh, Isere and Al-hassan, (2023) obtained similar results.

Error Correction Model (ECM)

Where co-integration exists among series, then the next step is to construct an error correction mechanism to model dynamic relationship. The real essence of the error correction model is to display the speed of adjustment from the short run equilibrium to the long run equilibrium state. The greater the co-efficient of the parameter, the higher the speed of adjustment of the model from the short run to the long run.

Table 4. Parsimonious Error Correction Model (1980 -2023)

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	T*	Prob
D(MPR)	27.51145	41.46110	0.663549	0.5126
D(MPR(-1))	239.8857	38.12441	6.292182	0.0000
D(MRR)	-8.871740	69.34961	-0.127928	0.8992
D(MRR(-1))	-231.1399	65.59227	-3.523889	0.0015
D(OMO)	0.310391	9.446831	0.032857	0.9740
D(OMO(-1))	-0.041666	0.204825	-0.203421	0.8403
ECM(-1)	-0.68.4141	20.25883	2.060862	0.4533
R ² 0.778822	Adj. R ² =0.568743	DW= 4.586539		

Source: Author Computation (EVIEW 13.0)

The result from table 4 reveals that the Adjusted R² is 0.568743 which designate that about 56 per cent of the systematic variation in the agricultural sector gross domestic product is explained by the independent variables in the model. The remaining 44 per cent is attributed to variables not included in the model but are captured by the error term. The outcome likewise explains that DW statistic value is 4.586539 and represents absence of first –order serial autocorrelation in the model. The error correction coefficient ECM (-1) value is -0.68.4141 or 68 per cent and is correctly signed with the expected negative sign and very significant. This submits that agricultural sector gross domestic product in Nigeria adjust speedily to the changes in the explanatory variables. Therefore, the ECM (-1) is able to adjust, correct and tie any deviations from the long –run relationship between agricultural sector output and the explanatory variables. The above result confirms with the results obtained by Owolabi and Adegbite, 2017; Owolabi and Adegbite, 2014; Ughulu and Agbonkhese, 2020).

Stability Test

The CUSUM of square test indicates that there is stability within the review periods in the model from 1980- 2023.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

This study empirically investigated effect of monetary policy instruments measures purely on agricultural gross domestic product in Nigeria, spanning between 1980 to 2023. Specifying a regression mode, we estimated empirically to establish the association between agricultural gross domestic product and the explanatory variables. The variables are agricultural gross domestic product sector output, cash reserve ratio, liquidity ratio, open market operation, monetary policy rate, minimum rediscount ratio and treasury bill. The variables were tested for stationarity using unit root, co-integration analysis and as well as error correction test was performed. The study found that the agricultural gross domestic product has a long run link with the independent variables. It equally revealed that all the variables in the model are very significant. The study consequently conclude that the monetary policy instruments have significant effect on agricultural output in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Grounded on the findings, the study recommends the following:

- The Central Bank of Nigeria should ensure that the monetary policies are perfectly working and specifically make funds available for farmers to borrow.
- The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should place more emphasis on expansionary monetary policy framework with a view to increasing monetary aggregates to boost output in the agricultural sector.
- Government should equally encourage the agricultural sector by providing the needed secured environment for farmers to operate.
- Lending rate should be reduced to encourage borrowing and hence expand investment in the agricultural sector.

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